

Personalizing Second Language Learning: Integrating AI with Learner Preference, Proficiency, and Engagement

Alireza Gharahighehi*
Itec, imec research group at
KU Leuven, Belgium
alireza.gharahighehi@kuleuven.be

Sameh Said-Metwaly†
Itec, imec research group at
KU Leuven, Belgium
sameh.metwaly@kuleuven.be

Robbe D'hondt*
Itec, imec research group at
KU Leuven, Belgium
robbe.dhondt@kuleuven.be

Felipe Kenji Nakano*
Itec, imec research group at
KU Leuven, Belgium
felipekenji.nakano@kuleuven.be

Ann Fastré†§
Itec, imec research group at
KU Leuven, Belgium
ann.fastre@kuleuven.be

Helena Van Nuffel
Centre for Language and Education at
KU Leuven, Belgium
helena.vannuffel@kuleuven.be

Wim Van Den Noortgate†
Itec, imec research group at
KU Leuven, Belgium
wim.vandennoortgate@kuleuven.be

Piet Desmet‡
Itec, imec research group at
KU Leuven, Belgium
piet.desmet@kuleuven.be

Pedro Ilídio*
Itec, imec research group at
KU Leuven, Belgium
pedro.ilidio@kuleuven.be

Ann-Sophie Noreillie‡
Itec, imec research group at
KU Leuven, Belgium
annsophie.noreillie@kuleuven.be

Anaïs Tack‡
Itec, imec research group at
KU Leuven, Belgium
anais.tack@kuleuven.be

Changsheng Chen†
Itec, imec research group at
KU Leuven, Belgium
changsheng.chen@kuleuven.be

Lucy Van Kleunen*
Itec, imec research group at
KU Leuven, Belgium
lucy.vankleunen@kuleuven.be

Fien Depaepe†
Itec, imec research group at
KU Leuven, Belgium
fien.depaepe@kuleuven.be

Celine Vens*
Itec, imec research group at
KU Leuven, Belgium
celine.vens@kuleuven.be

Frederik Cornillie‡
Itec, imec research group at
KU Leuven, Belgium
frederik.cornillie@kuleuven.be

Personalization has become a cornerstone of online learning platforms, offering tailored experiences that enhance learner engagement, satisfaction, and performance. Moving beyond one-size-fits-all approaches, personalized systems can provide flexible access, improve efficiency, and support both cognitive and non-cognitive development. In language learning, personalization affords increased motivation, self-efficacy, confidence, and technology acceptance, while reducing instructor workload. Despite these benefits, many language learning platforms remain non-personalized. This study explores the integration of personalization in an online language learning platform, simultaneously taking into account three latent learner variables: preference, proficiency, and engagement. Preference captures learners' thematic and content choices, proficiency reflects their level of knowledge and skills based on their performance in the online learning environment, and engagement measures their sustained interaction with the learning materials and risk of dropout. By personalizing based on these learner variables, we aim to tailor learning materials that align with learners' interests, match their abilities, and foster sustained participation. We validate our approach in the use case of learning Dutch as a second language, utilizing data from the free online platform NedBox, targeted at newcomers in Flanders. Across the three personalization variables, the experiments reveal that lightweight recommender systems outperform deep models for preference prediction, DeepIRT offers the strongest yet interpretable proficiency estimates, whereas random survival forest, particularly when augmented with those proficiency estimates, offers the most effective modeling of learner engagement. In line with teachers' views on meaningful personalization, these models can enable relevant recommendations regarding learning materials, driven by learner preference and engagement, as well as proficiency-aligned entry points into exercises. The source code is available at <https://gitlab.kuleuven.be/kor-itec/XAI4PEPOL>.

Keywords: computer-assisted language learning, personalization, proficiency modeling, knowledge tracing, dropout prediction, survival analysis, recommendation systems

1. INTRODUCTION

In order to learn a second language (L2) effectively, learners need plenty of opportunities to engage with the target language through comprehensible input and interaction. One approach to provide these opportunities is through authentic content that is pedagogically curated and, ideally, personalized (i.e., tailored to the individual L2 learner). Such content can be derived from audiovisual materials such as those found on online video platforms typically used by L2 learners in out-of-class settings, and needs to be carefully selected so that it features topics that are directly relevant for them to achieve communicative goals in the L2 (for example, finding a job). Crucially, even if selected to meet such learner needs, authentic content needs to be adapted so that it can serve as comprehensible input for L2 learning. Characteristic of the audience of adult L2 learners is their great diversity in terms of factors like prior language knowledge, the time they have available for formal learning, their level of engagement with the target language outside of the classroom, their ability to self-regulate their learning process, and their motivational beliefs. This diversity in profiles calls for personalization of content for L2 learning, which is

*This author is also affiliated to Department of Public Health and Primary Care, KU Leuven, Belgium

†This author is also affiliated to Faculty of Psychology and Educational Sciences, KU Leuven, Belgium

‡This author is also affiliated to Research Unit Linguistics, Faculty of Arts, KU Leuven, Belgium

§This author is also affiliated to Behavioral Science Institute at Radboud University and NOLAI (National Education Lab AI in the Netherlands)

hard—if not impossible—for teachers to achieve on their own.

While digital technologies have long been leveraged to design computer-assisted language learning environments that comply with principles of effective L2 acquisition such as comprehensible input and interaction (Chapelle, 1998), techniques for analyzing big data have more recently found their way into research on L2 learning, among other goals with a view to designing data-driven adaptive systems (Alexopoulou et al., 2022). Empirical research on the effectiveness of adaptive systems for L2 learning is scant, likely due to the notoriously complex nature of developing such systems for the ill-defined domain of L2 learning (Slavuj et al., 2017). Empirical research in the wider area of technology-enhanced learning indicates that adaptive systems can enhance cognitive learning outcomes by aligning instructional content with learners’ individual needs and preferences (Zhang and Aslan, 2021). Personalized environments also support non-cognitive outcomes, including heightened motivation (Pardini et al., 2022; Vanbecelaere et al., 2023), stronger self-efficacy and confidence (Chen et al., 2021), improved learning efficiency (Debeer et al., 2021), retention and more positive attitudes toward language acquisition (Gordon et al., 2016), and increased learners’ acceptance of the technologies used throughout the learning process (Chen et al., 2021). Beyond learner-focused benefits, personalization can reduce instructors’ workload as they are increasingly faced with heterogeneous learner populations (Holmes et al., 2019), although empirical research on this topic is in its infancy.

Various learner variables can serve as the basis for personalization, including cognitive, motivational, affective, and socio-cultural factors (Plass and Pawar, 2020; Gharahighehi et al., 2024). Previous studies on personalized learning largely examined adaptivity through the lens of a single learner variable, whereas the present study seeks to investigate how adaptivity operates based on multiple learner variables. In this study, personalization in L2 learning is approached through the lens of cognitive and motivational variables. More specifically, we focus on preference, proficiency, and engagement. Preference refers to learners’ tendencies to favor specific themes or types of learning materials, as indicated by their interactions, such as clicking on particular content. Proficiency reflects the learners’ knowledge levels, which can be assessed through their performance on exercises. Engagement captures the extent to which learners interact with and complete a sequence of exercises, or whether they disengage and drop out.

In this paper, we use Nedbox as a use case to study data-driven personalization in L2 learning. Nedbox is a free and open online learning environment designed for newcomers who wish to learn Dutch as L2 in Flanders, the Dutch-speaking part of Belgium. It is typically used as a supplementary tool alongside a course or textbook. The learning materials are linked to one or more themes (e.g., “Werk”¹ in Figure 1a). Each learning material includes a short article or video as a starting point (e.g., “Tram 44” and “Met de fiets naar school”² in Figure 1a), accompanied by interactive exercises. Each exercise targets a specific language skill, such as listening or reading. The difficulty is indicated by four levels, alpha being the easiest and three stars the most challenging. This difficulty is reflected in both the exercises and the articles, with shorter texts provided at the easiest level (See Figure 1b). Currently, there is no automated personalization in the platform. For more information on the design of Nedbox, we refer readers to Schiepers et al. (2016).

Three locations in Nedbox are considered for applying personalization based on the three

¹“Work” in English

²“Biking to school” in English

Figure 1: Screenshots from Nedbox.

mentioned learner variables: learning materials on the homepage (see Figure 1a), difficulty level on the learning-material webpage (see top left of Figure 1b), and order of competencies, i.e., language skills (see bottom right of Figure 1b). The overall idea is to recommend learning materials that align with learners' interests, match their knowledge level, and are likely to engage them, i.e., materials with a low risk of dropout. To our knowledge, this is the first study to examine these three personalization variables collectively within an online learning platform. The general aim of this study is to analyze learner variables that are important for personalization in computer-assisted language learning, particularly in the context of Nedbox, and to model these variables using suitable AI methods. In addition, the study evaluates these models for their personalization performance while considering potential synergies among the variables. Specifically, we aim to address the following research questions (RQs):

- **RQ1:** How can the L2 learning experience be personalized in the context of Nedbox?
- **RQ2:** Which types of AI methods are most suitable for this personalization?
- **RQ3:** Can personalization models targeting learners' preferences, proficiency, and engagement synergistically enhance one another's performance?

The remainder of this work is organized as follows: the related studies about personalized L2 learning are discussed in Section 2. The methodology and experimental setup to answer the outlined research questions are explained in Section 3. The results of the experiments are reported and discussed in Sections 4 and 5, respectively. Finally, we conclude and outline some directions for future work in Section 6.

2. RELATED WORK

Main aspects of personalized learning are categorized into the source, target, and pathway of adaptation (Vandewaetere et al., 2011). The source typically refers to the learner models, the target describes what needs to be adapted based on the source, and the pathway represents the translation between the source and the target. The extensive body of literature on personalized

L2 learning primarily focuses on cognitive-based personalization and is largely dedicated to English as L2 (Ismail et al., 2016; Slavuj et al., 2017). Most studies on L2 learning personalize learning experience based on learner models, either to match the learner's proficiency, i.e., their skills and knowledge level, or to align with their preferences (Chen et al., 2021). These approaches are mainly applied to the learning of vocabulary (Xie et al., 2015; Laaribi, 2024; Zou et al., 2021; Chen and Li, 2010; Aravind et al., 2025) and grammar (Fang et al., 2018; Zhao et al., 2013; Ni et al., 2025). As for skills development, there is work on adaptive captions for listening in English as L2 (Mirzaei and Meshgi, 2019) and on adaptive spoken dialogue systems for learning French as L2 (Cornillie et al., 2025).

To model learner knowledge, Knowledge Tracing (KT) methods can be used. KT approaches fall into two broad categories: traditional models, such as Bayesian KT and factor-analysis methods, and deep KT models. Bayesian KT (Corbett and Anderson, 1994) represents learning as the gradual mastery of skills through repeated practice. Factor-analysis approaches, most notably Item Response Theory (IRT) (Wilson and De Boeck, 2004), estimate student performance using a logistic function based on latent learner and item parameters. Deep KT began with the Deep Knowledge Tracing (DKT) model (Piech et al., 2015), which uses Long Short-Term Memory networks to capture temporal learning patterns, followed by models such as AKT (Ghosh et al., 2020) and DeepIRT (Yeung, 2019). While most deep KT models lack inherent interpretability, DeepIRT provides interpretable proficiency estimates through its integration of an IRT layer. In systems for personalized L2 learning that model learners' knowledge, both traditional methods (Zhao et al., 2013; Ni et al., 2025) and deep knowledge tracing approaches (Tang et al., 2024; Ruan et al., 2021) are employed to estimate a language learner's current proficiency. Deep knowledge tracing methods have demonstrated superior predictive performance compared to traditional approaches (Tang et al., 2024).

Recommender systems have been applied in educational settings to personalize learning experiences according to users' preferences, including in domains such as MOOC recommendation (Zhang et al., 2019; Gharahighehi et al., 2023), book recommendation (Devika et al., 2016; Sirikayon et al., 2018), and learning path recommendation (Rahayu et al., 2023; Ildio et al., 2024). Studies on personalized L2 learning that incorporate learners' interests often utilize recommender systems to identify the most relevant learning materials based on learners' preferences and learning styles (Feng and Zhang, 2025).

Most studies on engagement and dropout prediction have been conducted in the context of MOOCs (Dalipi et al., 2018; Wintermute et al., 2021). This is largely due to the relatively high dropout rates in MOOCs (Chen et al., 2024), which make it necessary to identify learners at risk of dropout and the factors that contribute to it. In the context of personalized L2 learning, however, relatively few studies have examined dropout modeling. Research adopting a longitudinal perspective has primarily relied on statistical survival analysis approaches, e.g., Cox models, to model dropout in L2 learning (Hwang et al., 2024; Beardsley, 2015). In contrast, non-longitudinal studies have predominantly employed logistic regression (Dahman and Dağ, 2019; Saito, 2000).

Although personalization has become a central theme in computer-assisted language learning, existing work typically focuses on isolated learner variables, such as proficiency level or learner preferences, rather than adopting a more holistic approach. To the best of our knowledge, no prior study has modeled personalized L2 learning by considering multiple learner dimensions, including proficiency, preferences, and engagement. Moreover, research on personalized L2 learning specifically designed for Dutch as L2 remains scarce, leaving an important

gap in both theory and practice that this work aims to address. Therefore, the gap we aim to fill is the development of a comprehensive approach for personalized L2 learning that integrates multiple learner variables, namely, proficiency, preferences, and engagement, within a single language-learning platform specifically tailored to Dutch as L2.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. CASE DESCRIPTION

As indicated in Section 1, this study is based on Nedbox, a website offering learning materials and exercises designed to support users learn and practice Dutch as a second language. As shown in Figure 1a, users are presented with a list of diverse learning materials—articles and videos—organized by themes. In total, there are 764 learning materials, including 547 videos and 217 articles, distributed across ten themes³.

When a user clicks on one of these learning materials, a sequence of exercises appears alongside the selected item, as illustrated in Figure 1b. Each exercise is associated with a difficulty level (ranging from level α , the easiest, to three-star, the most difficult) and targets a specific language skill. In the context of Nedbox, each sequence of exercises connected to the same difficulty level and language skill is referred to as a “publication”. Table 1 summarizes the number of publications and exercises categorized by difficulty level and language skill. Speaking and writing exercises are much less common than those targeting other skills, as productive skills are inherently more difficult to design and reliably assess in an online setting.

Table 1: Number of publications (the first element) and exercises (the second element) per language skill and difficulty level (α is the easiest and 3-star the most difficult level).

	Listening	Reading	Vocabulary	Grammar	Writing	Speaking	Total
α	(6, 25)	(98, 882)	-	-	-	-	(104, 907)
1-star	(551, 1978)	(830, 2402)	(493, 1152)	(74, 177)	(41, 60)	(30, 52)	(2019, 5821)
2-star	(620, 2091)	(834, 2229)	(594, 1335)	(111, 264)	(52, 75)	(36, 63)	(2247, 6057)
3-star	(538, 1608)	(639, 1678)	(495, 1148)	(93, 204)	(45, 70)	(28, 47)	(1838, 4755)
Total	(1715, 5702)	(2401, 7191)	(1582, 3635)	(278, 645)	(138, 205)	(94, 162)	(6208, 17540)

The learners’ logs contain interaction data from 7,346 learners within the Nedbox platform. These logs include records of learning materials clicked, publications followed, and exercises answered. These logs are described in Table 2. The density values in Table 2 represent the percentage of observed interactions between users and learning materials, publications, or exercises relative to all possible interactions.

3.1.1. Features

In this study, we use two groups of features: explicit features and extracted features. Explicit features relate to the learning materials and exercises. Explicit features of learning materials include their content themes as well as text embeddings for articles and transcription embeddings

³The ten themes are: Consumer, The World, Really Happened?!, Health, Life in Belgium, New Life, Social Contact, Leisure, Children, Work

Table 2: Users' logs statistics.

	Learning Materials	Publications	Exercises
Number of interactions	49K	145K	510K
Density	2.4%	0.4%	1.1%

for videos, which are generated using Dutch transformers BERTje (De Vries et al., 2019) and RobBERT (Delobelle et al., 2020). For exercises, the explicit features consist of the difficulty level and the language skill targeted, such as reading or listening.

The second group of features is extracted features, which we derive from interaction logs. These logs provide information about how learners interact with the platform, including their activity patterns and exercise attempts, as presented in Ma et al. (2023). We extracted these features because no explicit user-level attributes were available due to privacy constraints. Table 3 presents these extracted features used in this work. More specifically, the features were extracted from the user interaction logs, considering their occurrences and durations, and grouped into three categories: exercise-count features, session-related features, and score-related features. In this study, a session refers to the session cookie associated with interactions of a single user with publications and exercises of a specific learning material.

The exercise-count features quantify the number of completed exercises by each user separately stratified by content themes (10 themes), difficulty levels (4 levels), and language skill (6 skills). The session and score-related features were aggregated using the operations: sum, maximum, mean, and minimum. For instance, the feature ‘‘Aggregated Global Duration’’ comprises four values summarizing the total cumulative duration, the maximum duration considering every session, the average session duration, and the minimum session duration. Skill and difficulty related features were extracted analogously. For example, the feature ‘‘Aggregated Scores per Difficulty’’ applies the same set of aggregation operators to the scores associated with each of the four difficulty levels (α , 1, 2 and 3 stars).

3.2. NEEDS ANALYSIS

To gain a deeper understanding of which aspects of the platform could most benefit from personalization, and to address RQ1, we consulted teachers. As they are highly familiar with the needs of the target audience, it was considered more valuable to begin by interviewing teachers and discussing initial implementations with them before proposing the interventions to learners. Consequently, six semi-structured online interviews were conducted with teachers who are familiar with the platform and use it in their classrooms or suggest learners use it at home. The participants were recruited through convenience sampling, as teachers who were accessible and willing to participate were invited to take part. Of the six participants, five identified as female and one as male. Three teachers had less than five years of experience with the target group, one had between five and ten years of experience and two had more than ten years of experience. Three target groups were identified: (1) ILT⁴, a centre for adult education at an academic level, (2) CVO⁵, a centre for adult education, and (3) Ligo, a centre for basic education which targets

⁴Interfacultair Instituut voor Levende Talen

⁵Centrum voor Volwassenenonderwijs

Table 3: Summary of extracted user features.

Description	Number of features
Exercise Count	
Number of Exercises per Theme	10
Number of Exercises per Difficulty	4
Number of Exercises per Skill	6
Session Related Features	
Total number of sessions	1
Aggregated Global Durations	4 (1 × 4)
Aggregated Durations per Difficulty	16 (4 × 4)
Aggregated Durations per Skill	24 (6 × 4)
Score Related Features	
Aggregated Scores per Difficulty	16 (4 × 4)
Aggregated Scores per Skill	24 (6 × 4)
Total	105

adults with a low literacy level. Two teachers from each of these three different target groups in adult education were interviewed. The sample was thought to be representative of the population targeted in this study.

The interviews explored teachers' perspectives on the personalization of the platform in greater depth. An interview guide was developed to cover key personalization elements while maintaining a consistent structure across interviews. Simultaneously, it allowed teachers the flexibility to elaborate on themes of particular relevance to them. The individual oral interviews were conducted online, recorded with consent, automatically transcribed, and manually checked. The semi-structured format ensured comparability across participants while preserving the richness of their narratives. The interview protocol and subsequent data analysis were structured around the predefined framework of locations (homepage, difficulty level, and competencies) and variables (preference, proficiency, and engagement) for personalizing the Nedbox environment. The data were coded deductively to generate a matrix overview of teachers' preferences for personalization for each location and variable, as well as inductively to identify recurring themes for further personalization (Braun and Clarke, 2006). To address RQ2, the following three subsections (3.3, 3.4, and 3.5) explain the AI methods used to model learner variables as discussed in the interviews.

3.3. PREFERENCE MODELING

To model the interest of the learners, i.e., their preference over learning materials, Recommendation Systems (RSs) can be applied. There are two main categories of RSs: Content-Based filtering (CB) and Collaborative Filtering (CF) (Lu et al., 2015). CB recommenders suggest items with features similar to those that the user has previously expressed interest in, while CF recommenders predict users' preferences based on the similarities between users' and items' past interactions. In systems with rich users' logs CF generally outperforms CB recommenders (Adomavicius and Tuzhilin, 2005).

Given users' previous clicks on items (in our case, learning materials), RSs aim to rank items that the user has not yet interacted with, based on the likelihood of future clicks. More formally, let the interaction matrix be denoted by $C \in \{0, 1\}^{m \times n}$, where m is the number of users, n is the number of items, and each entry $C_{ij} = 1$ if user i has clicked on item j , and 0 otherwise. Given user features $U \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times d_U}$ and item features $I \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d_I}$, the recommender system learns a function $\hat{C} \leftarrow f(C, U, I)$ that estimates the probability \hat{C}_{ij} that user i will click on an unobserved item j . The items are then sorted in descending order based on their estimated \hat{C}_{ij} values and recommended to user i .

The following methods are investigated as RSs in this study:

- **UKNN** and **IKNN**: User- and Item-based K-Nearest Neighbors (Sarwar et al., 2001; Lops et al., 2011) are memory-based CF methods that impute missing interactions between users and items based on the interactions of neighbor users/items.
- **IALS**: Iterative Alternating Least Square (IALS) estimation for matrix factorization (Pan et al., 2008) is a model-based CF method that utilizes the alternating-least-squares optimization algorithm to learn users and items latent factors.
- **MVAE**: Multi-Variational Auto Encoder (MVAE) (Liang et al., 2018) is a CF recommender based on variational autoencoders with the assumption that the user logs are from a multinomial distribution.
- **EASE**: Embarrassingly Shallow AutoEncoder (acronym in reverse order: EASE) (Steck, 2019) is a linear CF model based on shallow autoencoders (Cheng et al., 2016). Unlike models such as IALS and MVAE, which learn latent factors for users and items, EASE learns an item–item matrix. This matrix can then be multiplied by the interaction matrix c to predict the click likelihood for missing interactions.
- **RF**: Random Forests (Breiman, 2001) are ensembles of decision trees employing tree-wise bootstrapping of training instances and node-wise random sub-sampling of features. In our setting, it is applied in a global fashion: each user-item pair is considered an input instance. The feature vector of each pair is built by concatenating the row and column of the interaction matrix corresponding to that pair.
- **PentaForest**: PentaForest (Ildio et al., 2024) uses a total of five random forests: four local multi-output random forests are used to impute soft labels in the interaction matrix, which is then used to train a global random forest. The local multi-output forests take each user or item as an input instance, and consider predicting all of its interactions as a multi-label classification problem.

Since most CF baselines do not support side features beyond user–item interactions, we exclude side features when training the compared RSs to ensure a fair evaluation.

3.4. PROFICIENCY MODELING

To model learners' knowledge state, Knowledge Tracing (KT) methods can be applied. Given the previous interactions of a learner with items, i.e., exercises, related to different knowledge concepts, these methods (implicitly or explicitly) model learners' knowledge state and predict

the performance of the learner on unseen items (Song et al., 2022). More concretely, given learner’s history of interactions with items $H_{u_t} = \{M_{u_0}, \dots, M_{u_t}\}$, where $M_{u_t} = (i_t^k, s_t)$ reflects the interaction of user u at time t with item i_t^k related to knowledge concept $k \in K$ with the score $s_t \in \{0, 1\}$, KT methods predict the probability that the user answers the next item correctly:

$$P_{M_{u_{t+1}}}(s_{t+1} = 1 | i_{t+1}^k, H_{u_t}) \quad (1)$$

In this study we have used the history of learners’ interactions with exercises to train both traditional and deep KT models. Each exercise relates to one of the language skills (See Table 1) which were considered as knowledge concepts in the KT models. The scores on exercises are binary. The following KT algorithms are evaluated in this study:

- **BKT**: Bayesian Knowledge Tracing (BKT) (Corbett and Anderson, 1994) is a traditional KT method extensively used in intelligent tutoring systems to estimate learners’ mastery of specific skills over time and to predict their performance based on these mastery levels.
- **IRT**: (Explanatory) Item Response Theory (IRT) is multilevel model in which item responses are treated as first-level observations that are cross-classified within users and exercises, with users and items forming higher-level units (Wilson and De Boeck, 2004)⁶.
- **DKT**: Deep KT (DKT) (Piech et al., 2015) is the first proposed deep KT model that utilizes Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), specifically Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), to predict the probability defined in Eq. 1.
- **Deep-IRT**: This approach builds on the Dynamic Key-Value Memory Network (DKVMN) and incorporates an additional IRT layer that captures learner ability and item difficulty, thereby enhancing the explainability of the deep model (Yeung, 2019).
- **AKT**: Context-aware Attentive Knowledge Tracing (AKT) (Ghosh et al., 2020) employs a monotonic attention mechanism with an exponential decay function to diminish the influence of exercises completed long ago, effectively modeling the forgetting mechanism.

3.5. ENGAGEMENT MODELING

In this study, we model user engagement with publications, which are defined as sequences of exercises sharing the same difficulty level and targeting the same language skill and related to the same learning material. To quantify engagement, one approach is to measure the time elapsed between the start of a learner’s interaction with a publication and the point at which they either drop out or complete the sequence of exercises.

To model learners’ engagement with publications, Survival Analysis (SA) is used. SA encompasses a set of statistical and machine learning techniques designed to model survival data, which is data that captures the time until a specific event occurs (Clark et al., 2003). A defining feature of survival data is the presence of censored observations, where the event of interest remains unobserved. The most common form, right-censoring, occurs when the event does not take place within the observation period or when the learner is lost to follow-up before the event happens. The main advantage of SA methods is their ability to incorporate such incomplete data during model training, unlike traditional classification or regression approaches that typically

⁶Explanatory IRT analysis was conducted using the lme4 package (Bates et al., 2015)

discard censored instances. The definition of event time and censoring depends on the specific event being modeled.

In this study we model time-to-dropout. Therefore, the event time is the duration between a learner's first and last interactions with a publication they abandon. Learners who complete the publication by their last recorded interaction are considered censored.

Survival data typically consists of two components: a time variable Y , representing the duration of engagement with the publication in our case, and a binary indicator δ , which denotes whether Y corresponds to an observed dropout event ($\delta = 1$) or a censored observation ($\delta = 0$). Given the user features U and publication features I , an SA model trained on Y and δ can predict time-to-event for unseen publications of a target user. In this study, the following SA methods are considered:

- **CoxNet** (Simon et al., 2011): A penalized extension of the semi-parametric Cox Proportional Hazards (CoxPH) (Cox, 1972) model that regularizes the coefficients with a weighted combination of ℓ_1 LASSO and ℓ_2 ridge penalty terms (ElasticNet). The regularization aims to solve numerical instability problems in higher-dimensional datasets.
- **RSF**: Random Survival Forests (RSF) (Ishwaran et al., 2008) are an extension of the non-parametric Random Forests (Breiman, 2001) to specifically model time-to-event outcomes, through an adapted splitting criterion based on the log-rank test statistic.
- **XGBoost**: eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) (Chen and Guestrin, 2016) is a gradient boosting algorithm for decision trees, that has been extended to work for survival analysis outcomes using the Accelerated Failure Time (AFT) model.

3.6. MODELING SYNERGIES BETWEEN LEARNER VARIABLES

To integrate the aforementioned learner variables, modeled through RSs (see Section 3.3), KT models (see Section 3.4), and SA methods (see Section 3.5), two combination strategies were employed. The first strategy involves using the estimations of one learner variable as input features for predicting another. The second strategy consists of post-processing (re-ranking) the recommendations generated for one variable using predictions derived from another variable.

It is important to note that not all combinations of learner variables are feasible due to the structural design of Nedbox. Proficiency is modeled at the exercise level, engagement at the publication level, and preference at the learning material level. Consequently, engagement can only be augmented using predictions from proficiency models, and preference can be augmented using predictions from both proficiency and engagement. The reverse directions of augmentation are not feasible within the constraints of Nedbox design.

To enhance engagement models with proficiency estimates, the first combination strategy is applied: proficiency estimates are incorporated as additional features during the training of engagement models. In contrast, many RS baselines, in their default implementations, are unable to incorporate additional features beyond the interaction matrix when modeling preference. For this reason, the second strategy, i.e., post-processing, is used to augment preference predictions. In this case, proficiency estimates are used to adjust (re-rank) the initial recommendations of the preference model.

3.7. EVALUATION PIPELINE

As is common in RS and KT methods, we use a time-based train-test split (Meng et al., 2020) to evaluate the models described in Sections 3.3, 3.4, and 3.5. The split is based on interaction timestamps: the last interaction is assigned to the test set, while all previous interactions are used for training. Specifically, the last learning material, publication, or exercise that the user interacted with serves as the test instance for modeling preference, engagement, and proficiency, respectively. To tune the models that have hyperparameters, the same rule applied to form a validation set from the training set for hyperparameter tuning.

To assess the performance of the methods described in Sections 3.3, 3.4, and 3.5, we employ evaluation metrics which are highly common in each category. For recommender systems (RS), we use Normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain (NDCG) and Mean Average Precision (MAP), two common rank-sensitive metrics that assign higher rewards to relevant items (those in the test set) appearing near the top of the list, as well as standard classification measures such as precision, recall, and Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic (AUROC). For knowledge tracing (KT) methods, we adopt standard classification metrics, including AUROC, accuracy, precision, recall, F-score and Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC). For SA methods, we use three well-known evaluation measures, including two variants of Concordance Index (C-Index), namely, Harrell's and Uno's C-Index, as well as integrated AUROC. C-Index measures how well the model ranks participants according to their predicted risk of experiencing the event,

4. RESULTS

4.1. NEEDS ANALYSIS

In general, the interviews indicated that certain forms of personalization within the platform could be highly valuable to the target audience. In addition to the three learner variables for personalization, i.e., preference, engagement, and proficiency, the interviews also analyzed three potential locations for implementing personalization, i.e., at the homepage level (see Figure 1a), at the difficulty level (see top left of Figure 1b), and at the publication level (see bottom right of Figure 1b).

As far as the homepage is concerned, all teachers indicated that ranking the learning materials based on the learners' preferences was a valuable approach. With regard to the textual explanations for recommendations, these should be as concise and to the point as possible, using simple language to avoid confusing beginners. No consensus was reached on whether the explanation should remain visible at all times or only appear when hovering over the learning material thumbnail, as this may depend on the target audience. In addition to incorporating learning materials that align with learners' interests, some teachers suggested introducing a gentle 'nudge' mechanism to encourage learners to explore material outside of their usual click behavior (for example, by recommending an item from another theme). The proficiency parameter, which would make learning materials available that correspond to the actual proficiency of the learners, was considered useful by all the respondents. Finally, engagement, i.e., the likelihood of whether learners complete the exercises of a learning material or disengage and drop out, was a parameter that half of the teachers believed could be taken into account when ranking the learning materials. However, they recommended using this parameter only in the background, without users noticing it.

Regarding personalization of the difficulty level, proficiency was considered an important parameter to take into account, since learners would definitely benefit from seeing exercises that more or less match their proficiency level. All teachers also agreed that leading learners to their default ‘star’ (i.e., difficulty level) was a valuable approach. For this particular location, some teachers also considered an explanation useful. Adding engagement to the personalization in this location was not deemed necessary for four of the teachers, claiming that learners should also be exposed to learning materials outside of their usual interests; one remained rather hesitant, but the last one would also include this parameter because of an assumed impact on motivation.

Finally, personalizing at the level of the competencies (e.g., reading, listening, etc.) according to the learners’ performance (learner proficiency) was considered useful by all of the interviewed teachers. In contrast, reordering the exercises of competencies based on the engagement of the learners was not assessed to be of added value. Teachers felt that changing the organization of the competencies within a series of exercises would interrupt the didactic structure envisioned by the content developers.

As an open finding for additional personalization features, teachers suggested the possibility to adapt the support language based on proficiency level, e.g., avoiding use of the target language for beginners and, later, recommending to switch to using the target language as a support language for a more thorough immersive experience. They added that this feature should be reversible by the learners at any point.

4.2. PREFERENCE MODELING

Personalization based on preference is mainly featured in the homepage to recommend learning materials. As mentioned in Section 3.3, seven RSs are compared in this context. Table 4 shows the performance of these RSs based on AUROC, MAP, NDCG, precision, and recall. For NDCG, precision, and recall, the performance of recommendations are evaluated based on recommendation lists with lengths of 3 and 5.

Table 4: Performance of recommender systems (“Pr” and “Re” refer to precision and recall; “3” and “5” refer to recommendation lists with lengths of 3 and 5, respectively).

	AUROC	MAP	NDCG@3	NDCG@5	Pr@3	Pr@5	Re@3	Re@5
EASE	0.955	0.283	0.205	0.279	0.203	0.198	0.203	0.330
IKNN	0.955	0.275	0.195	0.262	0.193	0.185	0.193	0.309
PentaForest	0.953	0.258	0.187	0.244	0.181	0.168	0.181	0.280
RF	0.927	0.234	0.171	0.229	0.167	0.161	0.167	0.269
MVAE	0.949	0.222	0.149	0.207	0.142	0.145	0.142	0.242
IALS	0.719	0.137	0.103	0.140	0.099	0.098	0.099	0.164
UKNN	0.767	0.120	0.088	0.121	0.094	0.091	0.094	0.151

As reported in Table 4, EASE was the best-performing model across all evaluation measures, consistently followed by IKNN. The performances of IKNN and EASE were indistinguishable in terms of AUROC. EASE, a relatively simple and fast model-based CF recommender, outperformed more complex models such as MVAE and PentaForest in this recommendation task. Given the substantially smaller number of items for recommendation (learning materials in this

context) compared to users (learners), EASE and IKNN, both of which primarily rely on item neighbors and parameters, are also likely to scale more effectively in this context.

To investigate which features may explain the recommendations produced by EASE (the best-performing RS in Table 4), we train a RF surrogate model using user features (outlined in Table 3), learning material features, and the EASE estimates as targets. Figure 2 presents the global SHAP diagram for this surrogate model. As shown in the figure, the features contributing most strongly are the user’s total number of sessions (see Table 3) and the BERTje embeddings of the learning materials.

Figure 2: Surrogate model with EASE predictions

4.3. PROFICIENCY MODELING

As mentioned in Section 3.4, both traditional and deep KT approaches were evaluated to model learners’ performance on the exercises. As reported in Table 5, deep models consistently outperformed the traditional KT approaches; however, unlike traditional models, their predictions are not inherently explainable. The deep KT models, i.e., AKT, DKT, and DeepIRT, perform very similarly, with DeepIRT achieving slightly better results on the MCC measure. Deep models, and DeepIRT in particular, perform substantially better on the MCC metric compared to traditional KT approaches, indicating that they are more suitable for scenarios with highly imbalanced data (around 80% in the case of Nedbox). In addition to its stronger predictive performance, DeepIRT offers greater explainability than the other deep models by providing estimates

of user ability and item difficulty alongside performance predictions. These additional estimations are valuable for interpreting and explaining the model’s outputs.

Table 5: Performance of knowledge tracing models.

	AUROC	Accuracy	F1	MCC	Precision	Recall
AKT	0.75	0.81	0.89	0.32	0.86	0.92
DKT	0.76	0.81	0.89	0.26	0.84	0.95
DeepIRT	0.76	0.81	0.89	0.34	0.86	0.92
BKT	0.53	0.72	0.83	0.05	0.81	0.85
IRT	0.54	0.61	0.72	0.07	0.83	0.66

To assess the consistency between the DeepIRT estimates and the IRT estimates⁷ of learners’ ability and items’ difficulty, correlations between these estimates were examined. Since DeepIRT produces updated estimates of these parameters at each prediction step in user history, both the last and the mean estimates were considered. As reported in Table 6, the estimations of DeepIRT and IRT for both latent variables, i.e., learners’ ability and item difficulty, are strongly and statistically correlated.

Table 6: Pearson correlations between IRT and DeepIRT difficulty and ability estimates.

		DeepIRT			
		Difficulty (last)	Difficulty (mean)	Ability (last)	Ability (mean)
IRT	Difficulty	0.51 (p <.001)	0.66 (p <.001)	-	-
	Ability	-	-	0.51 (p <.001)	0.56 (p <.001)

4.4. ENGAGEMENT MODELING

To model dropout risk as an indicator of learners’ engagement with publications, as described in Section 3.5, three survival analysis methods, including one statistical and two machine learning approaches, were evaluated. As shown in Table 7, the machine learning methods, namely RSF and XGBoost, perform better than the statistical method, CoxNet, across all evaluation measures. It should be noted that the overall models performances are not strong, likely due to a lack of sufficiently informative features.

Table 7: Performance of survival analysis methods.

	Harrell’s C-index	Uno’s C-index	Integrated AUROC
CoxNet	0.526	0.527	0.514
RSF	0.559	0.529	0.548
XGBoost	0.558	0.517	0.566

⁷obtained using the mirt package based on a single-factor structure (Chalmers, 2012)

4.5. SYNERGIES BETWEEN PERSONALIZATION VARIABLES

In Sections 4.2, 4.3, and 4.4, the performances of the RSs, KT models, and SA methods were assessed independently. We then investigated whether synergies could be identified between these personalization variables. As reported in Section 4.4, the SA methods generally exhibit poor performance in this context, which we hypothesize is due to a lack of sufficiently informative features. To improve their performance, we incorporated estimated learners' ability and aggregated publication difficulty (i.e., the aggregated difficulty estimates of the exercises within each publication) by DeepIRT and IRT as additional features for the SA methods. The performance of the SA methods with these added features is reported in Table 8. As shown in the table, the performance of all three methods improved substantially, compared to the results reported in Table 7. Machine learning methods, specifically RSF, still perform better than CoxNet in all evaluation measures.

Table 8: Performance of augmented survival analysis methods with IRT/DeepIRT estimations.

	Harrell's C-index	Uno's C-index	Integrated AUROC
CoxNet	0.584	0.562	0.577
RSF	0.662	0.623	0.649
XGBoost	0.658	0.596	0.657

Figure 3 presents the global SHAP diagram for the RSF model augmented with IRT/DeepIRT estimations. As shown in the diagram, the IRT/DeepIRT estimates rank among the most influential predictors of the RSF outcome. This suggests that they provide meaningful information and should be considered important features when modeling engagement.

To evaluate whether incorporating proficiency estimates into preference-based recommendations improves performance, we re-ranked the top 10 learning materials recommended to each user by EASE, the best-performing RS reported in Section 4.2, according to their estimated performance from the proficiency model. In other words, learning materials in the initial recommendation list by EASE that received higher aggregated predicted performance scores from the proficiency model were moved toward the top of the recommendation list. The resulting lists achieved a slightly higher NDCG@3 (approximately +3%) compared to recommendations solely based on EASE predictions.

5. DISCUSSION

To advance the personalization of L2 learning in Nedbox, the perspectives of teachers who actively use the platform in their classrooms offer valuable insight. These teachers, who work with a wide range of learner profiles, from academic learners to professionals and low literate learners, expressed a shared concern regarding excessive personalization. They emphasized that while personalization can meaningfully support learners in certain contexts, it may be counterproductive in others. In particular, teachers unanimously opposed altering the predefined sequence of competencies based on learners' proficiency or engagement levels since it conveys unforeseen pedagogical implications. Another form of personalization they viewed as undesirable was the provision of lengthy, personalized explanations, which they believed could disrupt

Figure 3: RSF augmented with IRT/DeepIRT estimates

rather than enhance the learning experience. Instead, they recommended limiting textual explanations or replacing them with simple visual cues, such as arrows or color coding. Although teachers discouraged presenting such explanations to the learners, they acknowledged that aggregated versions of these explanations could be valuable for the website’s editorial team, as they may help the team better understand the learners’ needs and preferences.

The teachers identified two areas where personalization would be most beneficial. First, they supported personalization on the homepage, primarily driven by learner preferences and, to a lesser extent, by proficiency and engagement indicators. Second, they considered personalization valuable within the learning material page. Specifically, they suggested that exercises should begin at a level aligned with the learner’s predicted proficiency, rather than consistently starting from the default introductory level (i.e., the α or one-star difficulty level exercises).

Building on the teachers’ insights into where personalization should occur on the website and which learner variables it should rely on, the subsequent analyses evaluated the suitability of multiple AI approaches for modeling these variables. In modeling the three personalization variables, the application of three corresponding groups of data-driven AI methods revealed distinct patterns that merit further reflection. For preference modeling, relatively simple and computationally efficient recommender systems such as EASE outperformed more complex and deep models, including PentaForest and MVAE. This outcome suggests that, for preference-based personalization, models relying primarily on user interaction logs, rather than extensive per-

sonal information, may be not only sufficient but advantageous. Their reduced dependence on sensitive data also aligns with privacy-preserving design principles, an important consideration in educational platforms. Therefore, such RSs appear to be well-suited for supporting the recommendation of learning materials on the Nedbox homepage (see Figure 1a). Furthermore, incorporating proficiency estimates as a post-processing step for learning material recommendations provided by EASE leads to a slight improvement in recommendation performance measured by NDCG.

Modeling learners' proficiency through deep learning models based on logs of learners' performance demonstrated more accurate predictions compared to traditional KT methods. DeepIRT, in particular, not only achieved higher predictive performance but also offered interpretable outputs through its IRT layer. The alignment between DeepIRT's internal estimates and traditional IRT parameters for learner ability and item difficulty further demonstrates its consistency. These characteristics position DeepIRT as a strong candidate for proficiency-based personalization, where both predictive performance and interpretability are pedagogically valuable. Accordingly, DeepIRT appears well-suited for determining which exercise difficulty level (α , one-star, two-star, or three-star) best aligns with learners' predicted proficiency on the learning material webpage (see Figure 1b).

For engagement modeling, RSF consistently outperformed the CoxNet model and further benefited from incorporating proficiency-based estimates. This interaction between variables indicates that engagement is not an isolated construct but one that can be more effectively modeled when informed by learners' proficiencies. Consequently, RSF augmented with proficiency estimates appears to be the most promising approach for supporting engagement-oriented personalization within Nedbox, particularly on the homepage where it can help avoid recommending learning materials associated with a higher risk of dropout.

To contextualize the reported results, it is important to note that the evaluated models were trained on proprietary user log data from the Nedbox platform, which cannot be publicly shared due to ethical and privacy constraints. Consequently, external researchers cannot rerun the exact experiments reported here. To support methodological transparency, the accompanying source code (provided in the supplementary material) includes a synthetic example dataset that demonstrates how the evaluation pipeline operates. This allows readers to reproduce the procedure and adapt it to any other dataset that contains interactions between users and learning materials.

Additionally, it is important to recognize that these findings are specific to the Nedbox use case and may not necessarily generalize to other educational contexts with different user populations, content structures, or interaction patterns. This limitation should be taken into account when interpreting the comparative performance of the models: the main methodological insights remain applicable, particularly the demonstration that multiple learner variables can be modeled within the same learning platform, and also that their integration can have a synergistic effect on predictive performance and explainability. However, the relative ranking of models (for example in Table 4) should be understood as Nedbox-specific evidence rather than universally replicable benchmarks.

In summary, the proposed framework for personalizing the user experience in Nedbox operates as follows. On the homepage, learning materials are first ranked for recommendation using EASE predictions, which are then post-processed using the proficiency estimates produced by DeepIRT. From the resulting top-ranked items, those with a high predicted dropout risk, identified by the RSF model enhanced with proficiency features estimated by DeepIRT, are removed. When a user opens a recommended learning material (or any material outside the recommenda-

tion list), the default exercise difficulty level (α , one-star, two-star, or three-star) should match the user's estimated proficiency. The default difficulty level is determined by computing, for each of the four difficulty levels, the average probability that the user will answer the exercises of that level correctly (Equation 1) as predicted by DeepIRT. The level whose mean probability is closest to 0.75, representing exercises that are challenging yet not overly difficult (Jansen et al., 2013; Klinkenberg et al., 2011), is then selected as the user's starting difficulty level.

6. CONCLUSION

This study contributes to the field of computer-assisted language learning by proposing a data-driven approach to personalized L2 learning that simultaneously incorporates learner preferences, proficiency, and engagement, three dimensions that prior work has largely examined in isolation. By integrating qualitative insights from teachers with data-driven evaluations of multiple AI methods, the study demonstrates how personalization can be pedagogically sound while remaining technically informed. The findings show that simple recommender systems effectively capture learner preferences, deep proficiency-modeling approaches such as DeepIRT provide accurate and interpretable estimates, and engagement can be reliably modeled through RSF when informed by proficiency signals. Together, these results establish a multi-variable personalization framework tailored to Dutch as a second language, addressing a notable gap in existing research and offering a scalable foundation for implementing context-appropriate personalization in Nedbox.

In this study, we focused on the Nedbox platform because it provided access to both teacher expertise and extensive user log data, enabling an evaluation of the proposed personalization framework in a realistic setting. A limitation is that the results obtained here may not be fully generalizable to other educational settings. The relative ranking of the recommender systems in Table 4, for instance, may differ in environments with different learner populations, content structures, or interaction patterns. At present, no publicly available dataset offers user log information comparable to what is available for Nedbox, which covers multiple learner variables such as preference, proficiency, and engagement, and this lack limits opportunities for external validation. Importantly, the conducted study demonstrates that these three learner variables can be modeled within a single learning platform and integrated to improve their performance and explainability. This highlights the potential of multi-dimensional personalization in computer-assisted language learning environments. However, the best-performing model for each of these learner variables may vary across platforms depending on the specific characteristics of their learners and interaction patterns. Another limitation of this study is that the Nedbox user logs cannot be shared due to privacy and ethical considerations, which means that the accompanying source code must rely only on a synthetic dataset that mirrors the structure of the original data.

As a future research direction, we aim to examine additional platforms for computer-assisted language learning to assess the generalizability of our findings and further validate the proposed framework. We also plan to explore mechanisms for extending the user-consent process within Nedbox, potentially allowing new learners to opt in to sharing their interaction data with the research community. Such developments would strengthen both the reproducibility and the broader impact of research on data-driven personalization in computer-assisted language learning environments.

Moreover, our analyses relied primarily on performance data. While informative, such data capture only the outcomes of learning and interaction, not the underlying processes. Richer

process data (e.g., interaction patterns and navigation behaviors) could provide deeper insights into how learners engage with and benefit from the system. In addition, background and demographic variables could not be included due to privacy constraints, limiting our ability to examine individual differences and contextual effects. Future studies should integrate ethically approved background data together with fine-grained process traces to support more nuanced and explanatory models of preference, engagement and learning outcomes.

In this study, we followed an offline evaluation framework to assess the models' predictions for proficiency, preference, and engagement. While this is the standard approach for evaluating KT, RS, and SA models, online testing, such as A/B testing, would complement these results and help mitigate potential biases. Another aspect of this study that requires further examination is the way learner preferences were modeled through their click behavior. User clicks are typically influenced by the position and presentation of items, whereby learners are more likely to select items that are prominently displayed to them (Hofmann et al., 2014). A promising direction for future work is to investigate methods for mitigating or correcting this form of bias. Furthermore, we aim to investigate whether the performance of preference models can be improved when enhanced with estimates from engagement models.

DECLARATION OF GENERATIVE AI SOFTWARE TOOLS IN THE WRITING PROCESS

During the preparation of this work, the first author used Microsoft Copilot to proof-read the textual part of the paper. After using this tool, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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